

How to complete the Simplified_SSD2 template

Table of Contents

Table of Contents	2
Introduction.....	3
Macros security lock & enable macros, if needed	4
Instructions for completion	6
1. Sampling programme identification code (progId).....	7
2. Programme Legal Reference (progLegalRef).....	7
3. Sampling strategy (sampStrategy)	8
4. Sampling method (sampMethod)	8
5. Programme type (progType)	9
6. Sampler (sampler).....	9
7. Sampling unit size (sampUnitSize).....	10
8. Sampling unit size unit (sampUnitSizeUnit).....	10
9. Sampling point (sampPoint).....	10
10. Sample taken identification code (sampId)	11
11. Country of sampling (sampCountry).....	11
12. Year of sampling (sampY), Month of sampling (sampM), Day of sampling (sampD) .	12
13. Coded description of the matrix of the sample taken (sampMatCode)	13
14. Text description of the matrix of the sample taken (sampMatText)	13
15. Country of origin of the sample taken (origCountry).....	13
16. Area of origin for fisheries or aquaculture activities code of the sample taken (origFishAreaCode)	13
17. Year of analysis (analysisY).....	14
18. Identification code of the laboratory (labId)	14
19. Laboratory accreditation (labAccred)	14
20. Laboratory country (labCountry).....	15
21. Type of parameter (paramType)	15
22. Code description of parameter (paramCode)	15
23. Text description of the parameter (paramText)	15
24. Analytical method identification (anMethRefId).....	16
25. Analytical method type (AnMethType)	16
26. Analytical method code (anMethCode).....	16
27. Analytical method text (anMethText)	17
28. Result identification code (resId)	18
29. Accreditation procedure for the analytical method (accredProc)	18
30. Result unit (resUnit)	19
31. Result limit of detection (resLOD)	19
32. Result limit of quantification (resLOQ)	19
33. Result value (resVal).....	20
34. Result value recovery rate (resValRec) and Result value corrected for recovery (resValRecCorr).....	20
35. Expression of result percentage (exprResPerc) and Expression of result type (exprResType)	20
36. Result qualitative value (resQualValue)	21
37. Type of result (resType)	21
38. Evaluation of the result (evalCode)	22
39. Action taken (actTakenCode)	22
40. Conclusion of follow-up investigation (evalInfo.conclusion)	23
41. Evaluation comment (evalInfo.com).....	24
42. Restriction or exception (evalInfo.restrictionException)	25
43. Amendment type (amType)	25
Creating the XML and submission to the DCF	25
Submission of data to the EFSA DCF (Data Collection Framework)	27

Introduction

The 'Simplified_SSD2' template is an excel file which can be used to compile and report contaminants, food additives, and food flavourings analytical data in line with the [SSD2 \(Standard Sample Description 2\)](#) data model.

The data prepared for submission to the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) include a number of data elements which need to be accurately coded, applying the Standard Sample Description Controlled Terminology. The lists of terms are also referred as SSD2 catalogues. For instance, when reporting the chemical Cadmium under the 'coded parameter analysed' (paramCode) element, the code 'RF-00000150-CHE' must be used, as retrieved from the PARAM catalogue, specifically within the "chemAnalysis" hierarchy, which lists the reportable terms for contaminants.

The 'Simplified_SSD2' template, includes dropdown lists with available codes only for certain reporting elements. This implies that not all reporting elements have embedded codes. For example, the 'coded description of the matrix of the sample taken' (sampMatCode) and the 'coded description of the parameter analysed' (paramCode) elements require the use of EFSA's MTX and PARAM catalogues, respectively. Therefore, it is strongly recommended to consult these catalogues to ensure accurate reporting for these critical reporting elements.

For a comprehensive overview of the available catalogues and to perform efficient searches, it is recommended to use the EFSA Catalogue Browser. Instructions on how to use the browser are available in the [EFSA Catalogue browser Guide \(wiley.com\)](#). Alternatively, the catalogues (major release of the catalogues is scheduled annually, end of January) can also be accessed in excel format, as published on [Zenodo](#).

The current document provides a brief overview of the reporting elements that make up the simplified tool, along with their corresponding codes. However, for a more comprehensive understanding, it is essential to consult the Chemical Monitoring Reporting Guidance, available at this [link](#), since it is the foundation for this concise guide.

Macros security lock & enable macros, if needed

The updated version of the tool contains macros. Therefore, the first time the tool is opened a warning message might appear with a message of "Protected View" as shown in the figure below. If this happens, please click on the "Enable editing" button.

Continuing to open the tool a second security warning notifies that macros have been disabled. Please select the 'enable macro' option.

If the macros are not enabled the tool will lose all the functionalities and cannot create the XML output file.

If you do not succeed enabling the macros or you want to change the macro security preferences, please check the macro security settings of your computer (Clicking on the Macro Security button in the Developer tab you will open the Trust centre where the settings can be changed as well as the trusted locations settings).

Should you get the following type of message of blocked content (red status bar) please take care not to run the tool directly from inside the ZIP archive but extract it first on your computer. Once the file is saved on a trusted folder of your computer follow the steps below:

- a) go to the folder where you saved the file,
- b) right-click the file and choose Properties from the context menu,

c) At the bottom of the General tab, select the Unblock checkbox and select OK.

Instructions for completion

The 'Simplified_SSD2' file serves as a template for preparing datasets to be submitted to European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) via the Data Collection Framework (DCF). The column headings specify the required data elements, and in many reporting elements a brief descriptive comment is included.

As a quick reference, the column headings of mandatory data elements are highlighted **red** and optional ones (and/or dependent mandatory) are highlighted **orange**. There is one field heading coloured **green** 'resId' (Result identification code) which is automatically completed in the template from information provided in 'sampId' (Sample taken identification code) and 'paramCode' (Coded description of the parameter).

progId	progLegalRe Select_progLegalRef	sampStrate	progType
	#N/A		
	#N/A		

Figure 1 – Data input sheet showing column headings

The following section provides a brief overview of the data elements and their corresponding codes. As mentioned in the introduction, the mandatory data elements that require coding are listed below:

- 'coded description of the matrix of the sample taken' (sampMatCode – EFSA's Catalogue Browser: Foodex2 catalogue, please check Section 13 below)
- 'coded description of parameter' (paramCode – PARAM catalogue).

1. Sampling programme identification code (progId)

(Column A - **Mandatory** – free text). This code groups together samples taken under a specific programme/project, by assigning a code to the grouped samples. The field should be defined by the data provider. Examples could be:

'Food_CHEM_2021' or 'XYZ_2021_Flour' where XYZ could be the name of the organisation reporting the data and flour is the product.

2. Programme Legal Reference (progLegalRef)

(Columns B and C – **Mandatory** – text or code selection from drop down-list). The available reportable legal references are listed in column C, 'Select_progLegalRef'. Selections can be made from the drop-down list, and the corresponding code will automatically appear in column B.

B	C
progLegalRe	Select_progLegalRef
N215A	Commission Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006 (amenc ST
N215A	Commission Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006 (amenc ST
N216A	Commission Regulation (EC) No 1882/2006 (amenc
	Commission Recommendation No 307/2010
	Commission Regulation (EC) No 401/2006 (amended)
	Commission Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006 (amended)
	Commission Regulation (EC) No 1882/2006 (amended)
	Commission Regulation (EC) No 333/2007 (amended)
	Commission Regulation (EU) No 252/2012 (Repealed by Com. Reg. EU
	Commission Recommendation 2015/682
	Commission Recommendation (EU) 2013/647

Figure 2 – Selection of 'progLegalRef'

Alternatively, as columns B and C are interdependent, the code can directly be selected in column B, and the corresponding description of 'progLegalRef' will automatically appear in column C.

A new feature has been introduced to enable the reporting of multiple 'progLegalRef' codes, in column B concatenated by a "\$" separator (e.g., N023A\$N018A). Note that selecting multiple codes will not generate a description in column C (column will remain empty). A pop-up notification will be displayed, and if a selection already exists in column C, it will be automatically removed. This will not impact the produced XML file.

3. Sampling strategy (sampStrategy)

(Column D – **Mandatory** – code selection from drop-down list). The list of codes/descriptions available for the sampling methodology applied are given in Figure 3.

Code	Description
ST10A	Objective sampling
ST20A	Selective sampling
ST30A	Suspect sampling
ST40A	Convenient sampling
ST90A	Other

Figure 3 – List of sampling strategy codes

4. Sampling method (sampMethod)

(Column E – **Optional** – code selection from drop-down list). The list of codes/descriptions available to reference the legislation, protocol or other documentation describing the method of selecting samples from the food chain are given in Figure 4.

Code	Description
N001A	Individual/single
N002A	Pooled/batch
N003A	According to Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2022/1428
N004A	According to Commission Recommendation (EU) 2022/1431
N008A	Unknown
N009A	According to Dir. 2002/63/EC
N011A	According to Reg 333/2007
N012A	According to Reg 1882/2006
N013A	According to Regulation (EU) 2023/2782 (repealing Regulation (EC) No 401/2006)
N014A	According to Reg 152/2009
N015A	According to Commission Regulation (EU) 2017/644
N016A	Industry sampling
N017A	Official sampling
N018A	Official and industry sampling
N019A	HACCP and owns check
N020A	Not applicable
N021A	According to Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2021/808
N030A	Individual
N031A	Pooled
N040A	According to Commission Regulation (EU) 2017/644

N041A	According to Regulation (EU) 2023/2783
N042A	According to Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2021/808

Figure 4 – List of sampling method codes

5. Programme type (progType)

(Column F – **Mandatory** – code selection from drop-down list). This data element indicates the sampling programme applicable. The list of available codes/descriptions is given in Figure 5.

Code	Description
K005A	Official (National) programme
K009A	Official (EU) programme
K010A	Diet study
K012A	Industry/ private programme
K013A	Survey
K018A	Official (National and EU) programme
K019A	EU increased control programme on imported food
K028A	Survey - national survey
K029A	Unspecified
K033A	RASFF alert notification
K038A	Official (National) programme for Third Country Import

Figure 5 – List of programme type codes

6. Sampler (sampler)

(Column G – **Mandatory**- code selection from drop-down list). This element is used to report the person/persons responsible for taking the sample; the available codes/descriptions are given in Figure 6.

Code	Description
CX01A	Industry sampling
CX02A	Official sampling
CX03A	Official and industry sampling
CX04A	HACCP and own check
CX05A	Private sampling
CX07A	Official, based on Regulation 2019/627

CX08A	Academia/researcher
CX99A	Not applicable

Figure 6 – List of sampler codes

7. Sampling unit size (**sampUnitSize**)

(Column H – **Dependent Mandatory** – Numerical value is expected). This element is used to report how a sample is created before the analysis, providing information on the amount (a number) linked to the unit provided.

This element must be reported in the specific case of pooled samples by including the number of single samples pooled (a number is expected). The system will return an error message if this business rule is not followed.

e.g. 'sampUnitSize': 5

8. Sampling unit size unit (**sampUnitSizeUnit**)

(Column I – **Dependent Mandatory** – code selection from drop-down list). The codes presented in the drop-down list, can be retrieved from Catalogue 'UNIT' in Catalogue browser. This element is used to report how a sample is created before the analysis, providing information on the unit of measurement (e.g. 'Unit', 'Litre', etc.) linked to the amount provided.

This element must be reported in the specific case of pooled samples (e.g. code 'G005A' which correspond to the 'Unit'). The system will return an error message if this business rule is not followed.

e.g. 'sampUnitSizeUnit': G005A

9. Sampling point (**sampPoint**)

(Column J and K – **Mandatory** – code selection from drop-down list). This element is used to report the point in the food chain where the sample was taken.

The available reportable sampling points are listed in column K, 'Select_sampPoint'. Selections can be made from the drop-down list, and the corresponding code will automatically appear in column J, as shown in Figure 7. Alternatively, the code can also be selected directly in column J and column K will be automatically filled in.

J	K	L
sampPoint	Select_sampPoint	sampId
E010A	Border control posts	2025_Cheese
E352A	Manufacture of feed additives and pre-mixtures	25_feed_add
	Slaughterhouse	
	Cutting plant	
	Meat mincing	
	Meat preparing	
	Mechanical separation of meat	
	Other meat processing activities	
	Fish processing	
	Fish freezing	
	Fish processing activities, other than freezing	
	Manufacture of prepared animal feeds	
	Manufacture of compound feedingstuffs	
	Manufacture of feed additives and pre-mixtures	

Figure 7 – Selection of the sampling point

10. Sample taken identification code (sampId)

(Column L – **Mandatory** – Free text). Each sample must have a unique identification code, created by the data provider, to serve as a reference for the sample. The sample identification code can be a combination of text and numbers, with a maximum length of 100 characters. This code must be unique and, if multiple analytical results are reported for the same sample, the same unique sample ID must be used for all related results.

11. Country of sampling (sampCountry)

(Column M – **Mandatory** – code selection from drop-down list). This data element is used to report the country where the sample was taken. Figure 8 shows a subset of the codes corresponding to the names of EU countries that can be provided. Non-EU countries could be also reported using the different codes embedded in the tool.

Code	Name
AT	Austria
BE	Belgium
BG	Bulgaria
CY	Cyprus
CZ	Czech Republic
DE	Germany
DK	Denmark

EE	Estonia
ES	Spain
FI	Finland
FR	France
GR	Greece
HR	Croatia
HU	Hungary
IE	Ireland
IT	Italy
LT	Lithuania
LU	Luxembourg
LV	Latvia
MT	Malta
NL	Netherlands
PL	Poland
PT	Portugal
RO	Romania
SE	Sweden
SI	Slovenia
SK	Slovakia

Figure 8 – List of EU countries

12. Year of sampling (sampY), Month of sampling (sampM), Day of sampling (sampD)

(Columns N, O, P – **Mandatory** – numerical fields). The complete date when the sample was taken is mandatory to be reported. For a sample taken on 3 May 2022, the date should be reported as follows:

sampY	2022
sampM	5
sampD	3

Figure 9 – Example of reporting year, month and day of sampling

13. Coded description of the matrix of the sample taken (sampMatCode)

(Column Q – **Mandatory** - code selection from the MTX (FoodEx2 Matrix) catalogue). This data element is used to describe the food or feed product, or matrix sampled. The code reflecting the lowest level of detail is normally used (e.g. select the code for tomatoes instead of the code for Solanaceae). The code can be selected using the MTX catalogue or by referring to the catalogues published on [Zenodo](https://zenodo.org/). Additional guidance is available in the FoodEx webinars, accessible at: <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/events/event/180926>.

If the required codes cannot be retrieved, please contact for assistance data.collection@efsa.europa.eu.

14. Text description of the matrix of the sample taken (sampMatText)

(Column R – **Optional** – free text). After describing the matrix with the most detailed level of information available using FoodEx2 in the 'sampMatCode' field, this free text data element can be completed to report a full textual description of the product sampled and to provide additional relevant information. This will provide a possibility of crosschecking for the codes reported and could highlight any data quality problem at the data analysis level.

Kindly noted that for all records with the same 'sampId' the 'sampMatText' must be the same, otherwise a business rule will be triggered.

15. Country of origin of the sample taken (origCountry)

(Column S – **Mandatory** - code selection from the drop-down list). Report here the country of origin of the sample taken.

16. Area of origin for fisheries or aquaculture activities code of the sample taken (origFishAreaCode)

(Column T and U - **Optional** – code selection from drop-down list). For fish, seafood and other marine products the FAO fishing area should be reported. Choose from the text selection field in column U.

'Select_origFishArea' which contains the full list of reportable FAO fishing areas, and the code will be entered in column S 'origFishArea' as shown in Figure 10.

latCod	origCountry	origFishArea	Select_origFishArea
BE		M40	Atlantic Ocean
	BE	M481	Peninsular

Atlantic Ocean
Atlantic, Antarctic
Bouvet
Peninsular
South Georgia
South Orkney
South Sandwich
Weddel Sea

Figure 10 – Fish area text selection

17. Year of analysis (analysisY)

(Column V – **Mandatory** – numerical field). This data element is used to report the year of analysis of the sample using the year format, for example '2025'.

18. Identification code of the laboratory (labId)

(Column W – **Mandatory** – free text). A unique code should be reported to identify each laboratory reporting the results. The data provider should create the code.

19. Laboratory accreditation (labAccred)

(Column X – **Mandatory** – code selection from drop-down list). Report information on the accreditation (if accredited) of the laboratories that performed the analysis. The list of descriptions and the codes are given in Figure 11.

Code	Description
L001A	Accredited
L002A	Third party assessment
L003A	None

Figure 11 – Codes for Laboratory Accreditation

20. Laboratory country (labCountry)

(Column Y – **Mandatory** – code selection from drop-down list). This field is used to report the country where the laboratory analysis was performed.

21. Type of parameter (paramType)

(Column Z – **Optional** – code selection from drop-down list). This element defines/classifies the parameter (substance) reported, based on the following definitions:

Code	Description
P002A	Part of a sum
P004A	Sum based on subset
P005A	paramCode fully analysed

Figure 12 – paramTypes reportable

As of 2021, the 'paramType' data element has been made optional. Consequently, reporting of this element is no longer mandatory. If the 'paramType' field is left blank, EFSA will automatically assign a value (in those cases where the 'paramCode' and 'paramType' combination is unambiguous).

22. Code description of parameter (paramCode)

(Column AA – **Mandatory** – code selection from PARAM catalogue). The 'paramCode' data element corresponds to the substance analyzed and the code shall be retrieved by referring to either the Catalogue browser (choosing the hierarchy 'chemAnalysis' for contaminants, hierarchy 'addAnalysis' for food additives or hierarchy 'flavAnalysis' for flavourings) or the PARAM catalogue as published on Zenodo, in excel format (excel sheet 'term' and column 'chemAnalysisReportable', 'addAnalysisReportable' or 'flavAnalysisReportable'). The corresponding code for the contaminant/food additive/food flavouring analysed must be inserted.

For example, when reporting results for 'Ochratoxin A', the code 'RF-00000148-TOX' has to be used.

23. Text description of the parameter (paramText)

(Column AB – **Optional** – free text). This data element can be used to report additional information of the parameter. The use of the ampersand character (&) and any other symbol should not be used in order to avoid the creation of invalid XML files. The maximum number of characters for this field is 250.

24. Analytical method identification (anMethRefId)

(Column AC - **Mandatory** – free text). This data element is used to provide a code to identify an analytical method used by the laboratory to detect the presence of a substance. For example, if laboratory undertakes a GC-MS analysis for Lead in Honey the code could be 'GC-MS_Honey'. The maximum number of characters for this field is 50.

25. Analytical method type (AnMethType)

(Column AD – **Mandatory** – code selection from drop-down list). This data element is used to indicate whether the analysis was performed to detect the presence of a substance (screening) or to quantify/unequivocally the identified substance (confirmation).

The analytical method type is used to indicate whether the analysis was performed to detect the presence of a substance/class of substances ('screening' AT06A) or to quantify/unequivocally identify the substance ('confirmation' AT08A). 'Screening' code (AT06A) should only be selected when a qualitative method returns a negative result; 'confirmation' should be reported for quantitative/semi-quantitative analytical methods.

The following codes are reportable:

Code	Description
AT06A	Screening
AT08A	Confirmation

Figure 13 – Type of analytical method

26. Analytical method code (anMethCode)

(Columns AE and AF – **Mandatory** – code selection from drop-down list). In column AF, a list of commonly reported analytical methods for contaminants, food additives, and food flavourings can be found. The analytical method needs to be selected from the drop-down list in 'Select_anMethCode', and the corresponding code will be automatically introduced in column AE (as illustrated in Figure 14).

In case a used method cannot be found in the picklist, reference is to be made to the ANYLMD catalogue within Catalogue browser or the ANYLMD catalogue as published on Zenodo, in excel format. For support, contact data.collection@efsa.europa.eu

AE	AF	AG	resId
anMethCode	Select_anMethCode	anMethText	
F028A	LC-MS (quadrupole)		ES_2024_JJ0000784
F344A	GC-MS (Q)		IT_2021_BT0000124
F344A	GC-MS (Q)		GR_2025_AS000023
	ETAAS (GFAAS)		
	AES		
	ICP-AES		
	ICP-MS		
	Capillary (Zone) Electrophoresis (CE or CZE)		
	Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA)		
	Microbiological tests		
	Macromethod broth dilution and plates incubation (Dilution - broth on agar plates)		
	Neutralisation test		
	Complement fixation test (CFT)		
	LC-TOF-MS		
	GC-MS (Q)		

Figure 14 – Selecting the analytical method code

For the chemical contaminants, food additives and food flavourings domains, the system returns a warning message if the 'anMethCode' is reported with the code F001A which corresponds to the 'Classification not possible'. In case the generic code F001A is reported, a description in 'Analytical method text' (anMethText) is required.

From the ChemMon2025 data collection, for the additives and flavourings domains, the system will return an error message if the 'anMethCode' is reported as code F001A='Classification not possible'.

27. Analytical method text (anMethText)

(Column AG – **Optional** – free text). This data element can be used to report additional information on the analytical method. The use of the ampersand character (&) and any other symbol should be avoided. The maximum number of characters for this field is 250.

When the code 'F001A' (Classification not possible) is reported in the element 'anMethCode', then a description in 'anMethText' is expected (as indicated in the section above).

It is required that the 'anMethCode' (Analytical method code) and the 'anMethText' (Analytical method text) remain constant for all results that share the same 'anMethRefId' (Analytical method identification). An example is presented below.

Example				Combination
Lab	Result	AnMethCode	AnMethText	anMethRefId
1	1	F027A	LC-MS/MS	XX12_LC_MS_Lab1
	2	F027A	LC-MS/MS	XX12_LC_MS_Lab1
	3	F027A	LC-MS/MS	XX12_LC_MS_Lab1
2	4	F027A	LC-MS/MS	XX12_LC_MS_Lab2
	5	F027A	LC-MS/MS	XX12_LC_MS_Lab2
	6	F027A	LC-MS/MS	XX12_LC_MS_Lab2

Figure 15 – Examples of 'anMethCode', and 'anMethText' for results with same 'anMethRefId'

28. Result identification code (resId)

(Column AH – **Mandatory** – text). Each result should have a unique result identification code which is created automatically in this field by concatenating the code for 'sampId' (column L) and 'paramCode' (column AA).

This column is highlighted in yellow to indicate that it should not be manually filled in, as the values are automatically populated.

29. Accreditation procedure for the analytical method (accredProc)

(Column AI – **Mandatory** – code selection from drop-down list). This element describes the accreditation/validation status of the method linked to 'anMethRefId' (point 24). The codes available are listed in Figure 16.

Code	Description
V001A	Accredited according to ISO/IEC17025
V004A	Other third-party quality assessment procedure
V005A	Internally validated
V006A	According to OIE guidelines
V007A	Accredited and validated according to Com.Dec. 2002/657/EC
V008A	Validated according to Commission Decision 2002/657/EC, but not accredited under ISO/IEC17025
V999A	Not validated

Figure 16 -Accreditation procedure codes and descriptions

30. Result unit (resUnit)

(Columns AJ and AK – **Mandatory** - code selection from drop-down list). The element 'resUnit' indicates the units of measurement for the numerical values. The available reportable units are listed in column AK, 'Select_resUnit'. Selections can be made from the drop-down list, and the corresponding code will automatically appear in column AJ (Figure 17).

resUnit	Select_resUnit	resUnit
G050A	Microgram/kilogram	
G060A	Milligram/gram	
G060A	Milligram/gram	
G052A	Milligram/gram	
	Milligram/kilogram	
	Milligram/litre	
	Milligram/Milligram	
	Nanogram/gram	
	Nanogram/kilogram	
	Nanogram/litre	
	Nanogram/millilitre	

Figure 17 – Selecting the unit for the result

31. Result limit of detection (resLOD)

(Column AL – **Optional** – numerical field). The limit of detection (LOD) is the lowest concentration that can be determined to be statistically different from a 'blank' analytical result. Results with the LOD reported may be used by EFSA to assess new scenarios when estimating the consumer's chronic exposure. 'resLOD' must be reported if 'resType'=LOD (see point 37).

32. Result limit of quantification (resLOQ)

(Column AM – **Mandatory** – numerical field). The element 'resLOQ', corresponds to the numerical value of the limit of quantification (LOQ), and is the lowest validated residue concentration of the analyte, which can be quantified and reported by routine monitoring with validated methods. This data element is always required unless:

- unvalidated methods are used (infrequent cases);
- 'resType' =BIN, therefore, the 'resLOD' should be reported.

33. Result value (resVal)

(Column AN - **Optional** – numerical field). This data element is used to report the result of the measured concentration of the substance expressed in the unit specified by the result unit.

Please keep in mind that when `resType`='VAL' then it is **mandatory** to report the `resVal`. In addition, when `resType`='VAL', then `resLOQ` must be numerically lower than `resVal`.

34. Result value recovery rate (resValRec) and Result value corrected for recovery (resValRecCorr)

(Columns AN and AO – **Optional** – numerical fields). The `resValRec` is the recovery value associated with the concentration measurement expressed as a percentage (%). i.e. report 100 for 100 %. If the result value has been corrected for recovery, indicate 'Y' for Yes or 'N' for No in `resValRecCorr`.

If neither `resValRec` nor `resValRecCorr` are reported, the result expressed is considered as 100%.

35. Expression of result percentage (exprResPerc) and Expression of result type (exprResType)

(Columns AQ and AR – numerical and code fields). These elements are used to indicate when the concentration is expressed as a percentage of a component of the sample, for example, on a dry weight basis. In the case of food additives, `exprResType` must be reported (mandatory), and subsequently, `exprResPerc` should be also reported (dependent mandatory).

Codes for the `exprResType` can be selected from the EXPRES catalogue; also presented in Figure 18. `exprResPerc` can be used to report the percentage of a measured specific matrix component (for example fat or moisture component of original sample).

Code	Description
B001A	Whole weight
B002A	Dry matter
B003A	Fat weight
B004A	88% dry matter
B005A	40% dry matter
B006A	100% vol. alcohol
B007A	Reconstituted product

Figure 18 – Codes for reporting the expression of result type

e.g. 1. Results (moisture percentage) for heavy metals as occurred in seaweed samples expressed on a whole weight basis:

- `exprResPerc`: moistPerc=40
- `exprResType`: B001A

e.g. 2. Results for a fat-soluble chemical measured in a butter sample expressed on a fat weight basis:

- `exprResPerc`: fatPerc=80
- `exprResType`: B003A

36. Result qualitative value (resQualValue)

(Column AS – **Optional** – code selection from drop-down list). This data element is used for qualitative screening results (for example, biological tests). In those cases, the `resType` should be equal to `BIN` (see point 37) and the `resQualValue` must be reported with the value `NEG` (as the only accepted value). For confirmatory results or quantifiable results `resQualValue` must not be reported.

37. Type of result (resType)

(Column AT – **Mandatory** – code selection from drop-down list). Report the code for the type of analytical result obtained for a substance following Figure 19.

Code	Description
LOD	Non-Detected Value (<LOD)
LOQ	Non-Quantified Value (<LOQ)
VAL	Numerical Value
AWR	Value above the upper limit of the working range
BIN	Qualitative value (Binary)
CCA	Value below CCalpha (less than CC α)
CCB	Value below CCbeta (less than CC β)

Figure 19– Type of result

Please keep in mind that when resType='VAL' then it is **Mandatory** to report the 'resVal'.

In addition, when resType= 'VAL', then resLOQ must be numerically lower than resVal.

38. Evaluation of the result (evalCode)

(Column AU – **Mandatory** – code selection from drop-down list). Evaluation codes can be selected from the RESEVAL catalogue in Catalogue browser. This data element is used to report the assessment of whether the obtained analytical result exceeds any applicable legal limit for the sample. The available evaluation codes are presented in Figure 20. If there is no information on legal limits applicable to the sample, it is sufficient to report 'J029A', i.e. 'Result not evaluated'.

Code	Description
J002A	Less than or equal to maximum permissible quantities
J003A	Greater than maximum permissible quantities
J029A	Result not evaluated
J031A	Compliant due to measurement uncertainty
J037A	Compliant
J038A	Non compliant
J040A	Not detected
J041A	Detected

Figure 20 – Evaluation of the result

39. Action taken (actTakenCode)

(Column AV – **Optional** – code selection from drop-down list). Codes can be retrieved from the ACTION catalogue in Catalogue browser. This reporting element is used when a non-conformity is identified during the control activities or if a measured substance is found above the level of concern. Multiple actions can be reported (Figure 21).

Description	Code
Administrative consequences	A
Intensified checks before release	B
Follow-up action due to a residue of a pesticide detected in a EU sample, which is not approved for use in the EU territory	C
Denial of community aid	D
Destruction of animals and/or products.	E
Follow-up (suspect) sampling	F

Follow-up action due to the residue of a pesticide detected in a domestic product, which is not authorized in the country	G
Follow-up investigation	I
Lot not released on the market	M
No action	N
Other	O
Follow-up action due to a pesticide residue detected in an organic sample, violating the provisions laid down in the organic farming legislation	P
Rapid Alert Notification	R
Lot recalled from the market	S
Animals and products classified as unfit for human consumption	U
Movement restriction	V
Warnings	W

Figure 21– Action taken

40. Result assessment (evalInfo.resAsses)

(Column AW – **Optional** – code selection from drop-down list). This element can be used to report the single result overall evaluation ('Compliant' or 'Non-compliant'), e.g. when results are numerically above the legal limit (single result numerical evaluation) but deemed compliant by national expert judgement (e.g. by a national risk assessor) due, for example, to natural occurrence. This element is optional and can be different for each result in a sample

41. Conclusion of follow-up investigations (evalInfo.conclusion)

(Column AX and AY – **Optional** – code selection from drop-down list).

The element 'evalInfo.conclusion' can be selected from the drop-down list in 'Select_evalInfo.conclusion', and the corresponding code will be automatically introduced in column AW.

The comment element allows additional details on non-compliant results or non-conformities (Figure 22).

For the food additives and food flavourings domains, 'evalInfo.conclusion' is highly recommended to be used to indicate whether the food additive/food flavouring was specified on the label of the analysed product, or the positive analytical result was due to natural occurrence. The only options that can be reported for these domains are: C19A, C20A, C05A and their combination (e.g., C19A\$C05A and C20A\$C05A).

Code	Description
C01A	Accidental
C02A	Cascade use
C03A	Environmental contamination
C04A	Illegal treatment
C05A	Natural occurrence
C06A	Withdrawal period not respected
C07A	Withdrawal period respected
C08A	Long shelf-life product
C09A	Change in the legal limit throughout the year
C10A	Contamination during handling, storage, or transport of food item/crop
C11A	Contamination from previous use of a pesticide: uptake of residues from the soil (e.g. persistent pesticides used in the past)
C12A	Cross contamination: spray drift or other accidental contamination
C13A	Good Agricultural Practice (GAP) not respected: use of a pesticide not approved in the EU
C14A	Good Agricultural Practice (GAP) not respected: use of an approved pesticide not authorised on the specific crop
C15A	Good Agricultural Practice (GAP) not respected: use of an approved pesticide, but application rate, number of treatments, application method or PHI not respected
C16A	Residues resulting from other sources than plant protection product (e.g. biocides, veterinary drugs, biofuel)
C17A	Use of a pesticide on food imported from third countries for which no import tolerance was set
C18A	Use of pesticide according to authorised Good Agricultural Practice (GAP): unexpected slow degradation of residues
C19A	Yes, present on label/added
C20A	No, not present on label/not added
C98A	Other
C99A	Unknown

Figure 22 – Conclusion of follow-up investigation

42. Evaluation comment (evalInfo.com)

(Column AZ - **Optional** - free text). Provide further information on the evaluation if needed.

43. Restriction or exception (evalInfo.restrictionException)

(Column BA – **Optional** – code selection from the ADDFOOD catalogue and/or excel tab 'ADDFOOD'). This data element is used to provide the restrictions/exceptions of each authorised food additive across the different food legislative categories. It can also be used for food flavourings where the restriction/exception for their use are described.

44. Amendment type (amType)

(Column BB - Use only in the event of amending/deleting records in the EFSA DWH (Data Warehouse)).

The correction is made through the 'Update procedure' described in GDE2 Guidance (EFSA, 2014a):

<https://efsa.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/epdf/10.2903/j.efsa.2014.3945>

(Chapter 5.2 Amendment Operations p.18-30).

This process is called 'amendment' and allows changes to be made in the data already saved in the data warehouse.

More specifically, when an amendment is performed, a new unique XML file is created with only the lines that need to be corrected and is uploaded in DCF. The new XML file is transmitted as a new transmission and, once it is valid, is submitted and accepted.

The main steps to be followed are:

- change the lines which need to be corrected (please keep the original resId as it is since this is a key element to perform the amendment);
- at the last data element of each result of your data set (data element: 'amType') add **U** for updates (corrections) or **D** for deletion;
- create a new XML file only with the records which should be corrected;
- upload the xml file in DCF as a new transmission (using the button "insert new dataset") and once it is valid, please press the "submit" button.

Creating the XML and submission to the DCF

The XML file, which will be subsequently transmitted to the Data Collection Framework (DCF), can be created by right-clicking on any active cell of the excel table containing the records to be exported. The "XML" command, appearing in the context menu, shall be selected, and subsequently, the "Export" option should be chosen (Figure 23).

Alternatively, if the "Developer" option is activated in the excel, the "Export" option can be selected from the XML tab in the Developer ribbon.

The location where the XML file should be saved needs to be specified. It is recommended that the XML file is saved in the same local folder as the original excel file, allowing for easy access and modification of the dataset in the future, as well as maintaining a reference record.

Figure 23 – Creation of xml

Submission of data to the EFSA DCF (Data Collection Framework)

The Data Collection Framework is the EFSA interface for data submission is available at the following link: <https://dcf.efsa.europa.eu/dcf-war/dc>. An account is required to transmit data to EFSA. If you do not have a DCF account, please send an email to data.collection@efsa.europa.eu to request one.

- 1) Log in to the account using the username and password received via e-mail from the EFSA ServiceDesk, as in Figure 24.

Data Collection Framework

Welcome. Please, log in to your account.

Username

Password

Figure 24 - Log in page for the Data Collection Framework (DCF)

- 2) Expand the list under 'data collections' by clicking on the + sign on the left-hand side. Further:
 - a) Click on the + next to "Chemical Monitoring"
 - b) Click on + beside "CHEM_MON_SSD2_WF2"
 - c) Click on + "CHEM_MON_SSD2_WF2.2026" (Figure 25)

Figure 25 - Data collection selection

- 3) To transmit a new data set, open the folder for the current data collection, "CHEM_MON_SSD2_WF2.2026", click on 'dataset', and choose the 'insert new dataset' option, as presented in Figure 26.

Figure 26 – Transmission of a file

- 4) After clicking 'insert new dataset' you may proceed with uploading a data set, (XML file), as shown in Figure 27.

Figure 27 – Choosing and uploading an XML File in DCF

Do not upload the excel workbook, only XML files can be submitted.

Once the processing of the file is completed, an e-mail is automatically sent by the system verifying that the transmission of the XML file has been processed.

In case there is a validation failure, due to violation of business rules or controlled terminologies, the status of the dataset will be "Rejected" or "Rejected Editable". In order to see the reasons for rejection, the data provider can check the message attached to the email or alternatively utilise the options of 'ack view' or 'ack details' in DCF, as shown below (Figure 28).

dataset id	status	last update	user	table name	sender dataset id	confirmed
24475	Rejected Editable	2019-04-04 06:30:34	forguau		69475	

Figure 28 – Checking the acknowledgement messages ('ack view' or 'ack details')

An overview of the validation errors, indicating why the transmission has been rejected will be provided as indicated in Figures 29 and 30.

Summary of Errors/Warnings				
Type of validation information	Error or warning feedback	Example of checked record	Value	Number of Records
error	Term not found: the provided term code either is not present in the catalogue, or it is deprecated, or it is not reportable in the hierarchy associated to the data element.	labCountry	UK	2867
error	Term not found: the provided term code either is not present in the catalogue, or it is deprecated, or it is not reportable in the hierarchy associated to the data element.	resUnit	G057A	17
error	resLOD is not less than or equal to resLOQ;	resLOD	0.01	2087

Figure 29 – Information about the errors and/or warnings, as shown in 'ack view' option

List of Errors								
Business Rule Code	Type	Message	Error sequence	Context Description				
	error	Term not found: the provided term code either is not present in the catalogue, or it is deprecated, or it is not reportable in the hierarchy associated to the data element.	1	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>recordUniqueid</td> <td>paramCode.base.param</td> </tr> <tr> <td>samp1RF-00000114-ORG</td> <td>RF-00000114-ORG</td> </tr> </table>	recordUniqueid	paramCode.base.param	samp1RF-00000114-ORG	RF-00000114-ORG
recordUniqueid	paramCode.base.param							
samp1RF-00000114-ORG	RF-00000114-ORG							
	error	Term not found: the provided term code either is not present in the catalogue, or it is deprecated, or it is not reportable in the hierarchy associated to the data element.	2	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>recordUniqueid</td> <td>paramCode.base.param</td> </tr> <tr> <td>samp1RF-00005733-PAR</td> <td>RF-00005733-PAR</td> </tr> </table>	recordUniqueid	paramCode.base.param	samp1RF-00005733-PAR	RF-00005733-PAR
recordUniqueid	paramCode.base.param							
samp1RF-00005733-PAR	RF-00005733-PAR							

Figure 30 – List of business rules errors and/or warnings, as presented using the 'ack details' option

For a more detailed report on the errors choose 'ack details' (Figure 30). The downloaded file can be opened in notepad, excel or any xml application.

The xml file will provide more detailed information regarding the errors and related Business rules (BR). As shown in the example below, the 'ack details' will provide the Data provider with more information regarding the BR number, the unique identifiers as well as the different data elements linked to the specific error(s).

Most errors can be resolved by making the necessary corrections to the original excel file. For other types of errors, questions or clarifications please contact data.collection@efsa.europa.eu.

When the dataset is 'Valid' or 'Valid with warning' in the DCF the box next to the dataset which is 'Valid' or 'Valid with warning' should be ticked and then click on 'Submit' as shown in Figure 31.

Figure 31 – Submitting a dataset

The dataset is migrated to **MicroStrategy**. At this pre EFSA SDWH (Scientific Data Warehouse) stage you can visualise the data in the dashboards and reports. The appointed data validator can check the data in the validation reports and if no errors are identified 'Confirm' the data by clicking the confirmation button in MicroStrategy.

dataset confirmed		processing dataset		
Datasets Present in the Validation Dashboard				
Dataset ID	Dataset status decoding	Time of the transmission	Programme legal reference	Number of records
27030	dataset confirmed	8/29/2019 7:54:09 PM	Council Directive (EC) No 23/1996 (amended)	117
27076	dataset confirmed	8/29/2019 7:55:09 PM	Council Directive (EC) No 23/1996 (amended)	21,758
27077	dataset confirmed	8/29/2019 7:56:09 PM	Council Directive (EC) No 23/1996 (amended)	21,655

Figure 32 – Status of datasets in Validation Dashboard

In Figure 32, the datasets have been 'confirmed' by the data validator. The status of the data is 'Accepted_DWH'. At this point the data will be included in EFSA's SDWH (Scientific Data Warehouse) and available for use in EFSA scientific assessments.